

USE OF A MEDICAL TOMODENSITOMETER IN
NONDESTRUCTIVE TESTING OF COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

We present here, the results of researches about fitting and using of a medical scanner to control of composite materials by examining the rate of components, porosity and determining density and its fluctuations. Scanning allows also the detection of defects such as local porosity, delamination and inclusion. We study the evolution of materials submitted to constraint (humidity, heat, compression, etc...).

INTRODUCTION

As part of the effort to develop nondestructive testing methods for composite materials, we have been concentrating for several years on the use of X-ray tomodensitometer. Using a commercially available medical tomodensitometer with modified operational characteristics¹ for our industrial needs and objectives, we have attempted to define what the actual possibilities this state-of-the-art method are, making it worthy of participation in the future concert of major nondestructive testing techniques along with acoustical, ultrasonic and thermographic methods.

Essentially, we have oriented our studies in three directions, while aiming at a better characterization of the quality of manufactured parts independent of any utilization-related stresses, at the same time as we were trying to find out how the material behaves and its characteristics vary under the effect of everyday humidity and temperature stresses :

- 1 - Measuring the physical structure (density and porosity) of materials
- 2 - Recognizing and evaluating defects
- 3 - Evaluating of alterations in materials in reaction to various stresses

1 These modifications concerned the monochromism of the X-ray and the acquisition time.

I - Measurement of the Physical Structures of Materials

As the purpose of our studies in this field was to qualify the material, we were trying above all to determine the local density and porosity variations in the tested pieces, independently of their geometry.

The method involves a calibration on each constituent part to determine its own absorption coefficient.

By testing the production parts and standard pieces simultaneously, problems due to time variations in the X-ray beam emitted by the tube could be got around and a high level of precision could be achieved in the density determination. Comparisons with other methods show a large agreement among all of the measurement data, with a deviation of less than 0,5 %.

The advantage of tomodesitometry is that it provides a local map of density deviations regardless of the geometry of the piece, without having to fall back on testing samples.

Also, as a greater porosity of a material corresponds to a lesser density, the variations of the TDM number found when examining parts of different porosity can be used as a quantitative measure of these porosities. To do this, it is sufficient to determine the fiber/resin composition of the material and evaluate by calibration the theoretical absorption of the ideal zero-porosity material.

The volume of the piece taken up by porosities can be computed from the measured TDM number with a high level of accuracy.

It thus seems that tomodesitometry yields a great deal of information in this field, compared with the ultrasonic methods, for example, which can only reach thresholds of evaluation.

To quantify the constituent parts of the composite material within a piece itself, we have developed a "multi-energy" method using additional filters and based on the rule of adding together the absorptions per unit mass of each constituent part, but which seems to yield data for graphite/resin composites that is marred by a high level of inaccuracy due to too close a similarity in the absorption coefficients of the fibers and of the resin.

The accuracy is much better, though, for glass fiber composites and for those having metal components with absorption discontinuities in the power range from 70 kV to 130 kV.

An artificial hardening of the X-ray beam is nonetheless advised.

2 - Recognition and Evaluation of Defects in Materials

Needing no further proof of the extraordinary investigating power of tomodesitometry in visualizing common defects in manufactured parts, we attempted to define the detection limits of detection of simulated local porosities and defects (delaminations) of various sizes on composite samples.

We have found from our analysis that, though the size of the defect is an important parameter in detecting it by tomodesitometry, which of course depends on the fineness of the image reconstruction grid (pixel size), the other main parameter involved is the type of defect, i.e. its absorption level. In fact, the determining factor in calibrating the defects in composites appear above all to be the ratio between the absorption coefficients of the defect and the matrix. That is, even a fine delamination can be detected in the form of a film of air, while a simulation in an organic material of the plastic or kapton type, which is more absorbent and thus has a higher TDM number closer to that of the matrix material, will not be detected even if it is spread out over a large area of few square millimeters.

3 - Evaluation of the Modifications in a Material Subjected to Humidity and Temperature Stresses (In-situ test)

The classical stresses commonly studied (relative humidity, temperature, mechanical stresses) cause momentary points of damage that are actually local modifications in the state of equilibrium of the material and of its density and which are mostly not observable since they disappear once the stresses cease.

Compared with other methods of nondestructive testing, the tomodesitometer offers the advantage of being able to make in-situ measurements in continuous mode, i.e. directly in the material while it is being subjected to the stress. In particular, for example, the tomodesitometer appears to be a very sensitive method for studying the swelling of composites in moisture yielding more accurate information than the merely global weighing methods.

To conduct our study, we constructed a sealed enclosure in teflon for examining samples of composite materials under the combined effects of temperature and humidity.

We chose teflon because of its absorption compatibility with the relative low power of the X-ray beam of our medical instrument, and because of its resistance to temperature effects.

Two approaches were chosen using :

- 1 - Short, repetitive stress cycles
- 2 - Longer, continuous ageing cycles.

The damage caused during the stressing results in apparent density modifications within the material (TDM number).

When the stresses cease, the material relaxes and tends to return to its initial state of equilibrium. However, depending on the nature and parameters of the stress and of the nature of the material, a residual damage may remain locally, i.e. the TDM number of the material once returned to the initial conditions is different from the initial number of the material.

This difference thus indicates the existence of microstructuring or cracking in the fabric, or porosity changes due to the creation of new sites or due to combining porosity sites that already existed in the material but were too small to be detected individually beforehand.

Producing this way with several materials, each different in nature and in percent content, these analyses that we are pursuing by tomodesitometry may offer an excellent correlation among the various ageing phenomena and the nature of these materials.

It can, in particular, lead to use a better understanding of the humidity diffusion dynamics within the material.

We are continuing our study both on "healthy" materials and on those exhibiting defects ; thereby opening the way to learning how defects evolve and perhaps being able to judge the strength or weakness of a material beforehand.

Our findings have been very encouraging so far and the study is continuing.

CONCLUSION

Although recent, the application of tomodesitometry to the examination of parts made of composite materials seems to be competitive over other testing methods, in particular for thick parts, yielding dependable information on their makeup, their "health" and the alteration of the materials under stress.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

DETERMINATION OF MEAN POROSITY .							
Sample	Desired porosity	Tomodensitometer			pycno He .		US
429	8%	312	I.452	7.8%			not evaluated
432	3%	399	I.549	I.6%	I.547	I.68%	not evaluated
435	I%	435	I.585	0.6%	I.572	0.69%	I%
		NTDM	D.	P	D	P	

TABLE 4

Comparison of density measurements on composite samples by tomodensitometric ,geometric and hydrostatic methods .				
Sample .	Mat .	Tomo density .	Geo density .	Hydro density
3205		1.417	1.419	1.420
3208		1.432	1.435	
3212		1.430	1.428	
3002		1.435	1.427	
3011		1.428	1.429	
1222		1.532	1.532	
1229		1.547	1.553	
1230		1.584	1.578	
1705		1.603	1.600	1.602
1708		1.600	1.588	1.598
1713		1.527	1.514	1.527

TABLE. 3

FIG. 5